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Motivation

Micro-Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (hereby μ SOFC) are an emerging alternative for portable power supply due to their high volumetric power density (1000Wh/l) and specific energy (1000Wh/kg) - five times higher than current Li-ion batteries [1]. Moreover, its instantaneous charge capacity and outstanding high power density (1W/cm²) will allow increasing the limited off-grid autonomy of existing high performance devices.

Micro-SOLUTION project (GA 659270) explores the development of nanostructured ceramic thin film materials as anodes and cathodes for μ SOFCs.

Approach

In this work we propose **a innovative methodology for the preparation of new SOFC cathode formulations for μ SOFCs**. By **Combinatorial PLD** we have prepared a great amount of different compositions in one single experiment saving plenty of time in the preparation stage. Following procedure has been followed: **i)** Complete study of the parent compounds (previously attained [2]); **ii)** Combinatorial deposition; **iii)** Characterization of chip size samples, **iv)** Suggest an optimized composition.

Characterization

- Crystallinity (XRD)
- Microstructure (SEM)
- Compositional (EDS, WDS)
- Electrochemical (EIS)
- Surface (XPS, AFM)

Fabrication

Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) is a physical vapor deposition (PVD) technique where an energetic pulsed laser beam strikes a target of the desired material to be deposited. The material is vaporized (in a plasma plume) which deposits as a thin film on a substrate facing the target.

In **Combinatorial PLD** several targets are consecutively ablated while the substrate rotates generating a multilayer thin film. The distribution of thicknesses attained for each material will create the compositional map due to material interaction.

Experimental details

Cationic interdiffusion & Crystallization (high deposition temperature)

Dicing of the wafer (10 x 10 mm chips)

Combinatorial PLD simulation

Maximization of the extension of the compositional map generated by the combinatorial deposition was achieved by a MATLAB simulation. Plume overlapping have a strong influence in the extent of different compositions attained. Modeling of ternary deposition process allows us to control the compositional distribution throughout the wafer.

Main features

- No pure compounds will be present in our 3" YSZ - single crystal wafer
- Ternary diagram is distorted due to the stronger interaction of LSM and LSC with LSF
- Isolines does not match in the borders of the triangle due to presence of the 3rd material

Individual characterization

XRD characterization

Thin films fabricated by Combinatorial PLD show perovskite-based crystalline structure throughout the whole wafer (#). Minor peaks (not indexed yet) appear in very specific samples (#).

Diffraction patterns provide compositional information as well through peak position.

Wafer analysis status

In the following picture the characterization carried out until this moment is shown.

SEM characterization

Features

- Highly compact dense thin film
- Nanometric size grains
- High density of grain boundaries
- Heterogeneous grain growth

EIS characterization

Conclusions

- **Combinatorial PLD deposition** has been **validated** as high-throughput technique for fabrication of μ SOFC cathode materials.
- Ternary thin films show great crystalline homogeneity, nanometric grain size and columnar microstructure throughout the whole wafer.
- On going **characterization will provide an optimized composition for SOFC cathode starting from LSM/LSC/LSF ternary system**.

EDS characterization

Assessment of the compositional map obtained was firstly made by Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy.

Features

- Elemental distribution is in good agreement with simulated ternary diagram
- Small differences are attributed to overlapping of Mn, Co and Fe contributions

References:

- [1] A. Evans, A. Bieberle-Hütter, J. L.M. Rupp, L.J. Gauckler, *J. Power Sources* 194 (2009) 119-129.
- [2] A.B. Saranya (2015), *Integrating nanoionics concept in micro solid oxide fuel cells*, PhD Thesis, Department of electronics, University of Barcelona.

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